

DEVELOPMENT OF ATHLETES' ENDURANCE IN PREPARATION FOR INTERNATIONAL RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS COMPETITIONS

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Abstract. *This article, authored by Polina Makovska, explores various methods of developing endurance in athletes in preparation for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. Emphasis is placed on the importance of a comprehensive approach, including cardio training, strength exercises, functional training, flexibility work, and systematic training loads. This analysis provides gymnasts and their coaches with valuable recommendations for effective preparation for competitions at the international level.*

Keywords: *rhythmic gymnastics, sports training, endurance training, cardio training, strength exercises, functional training, flexibility, training load, international competitions.*

Introduction. Preparation for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions requires athletes to have high technical skills, expressiveness, and outstanding endurance. In conditions of competitive stress and prolonged performances, gymnasts need to possess technical skills and physical fitness, enabling them to maintain a high level of energy and concentration throughout the performance.

This article will analyze various methods and strategies for developing gymnasts' endurance during preparation for international competitions. We will consider effective approaches that help athletes reach their peak physical condition and prepare to deliver their best performances on the world stage of rhythmic gymnastics.

Research Objective. The aim of this study is to examine methods and strategies for developing endurance in athletes in preparation for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. The research will examine various aspects of the training process, including cardio training, strength training, functional exercises, flexibility work, and systematic training loads. The main goal is to identify optimal methods and approaches for gymnasts to achieve high endurance and perform effectively on the international stage. The analysis of these methods and their application in the training process contributes to a deeper understanding of the requirements of modern rhythmic gymnastics and the optimization of athletes' preparation for competitions.

Methods. To achieve the research objective, I conducted a literature review on endurance training methods in rhythmic gymnastics and analyzed the experiences of coaches and athletes who participated in international competitions. Based on the obtained data, the main training methods were identified, and recommendations for their application in the training process were developed.

Cardio Training:

Cardio training plays a key role in preparing gymnasts for international competitions. In rhythmic gymnastics, where each performance requires high technique, flexibility, and prolonged concentration and energy, cardio training helps athletes improve endurance and resilience to physical and emotional stress during performances.

Effective cardio training includes a variety of exercises, such as running, swimming, elliptical training, or outdoor cardio workouts. It is important to consider each athlete's individual characteristics and goals and the specifics of the rhythmic gymnastics training process.

Regular cardio training improves cardiovascular health, increases lung capacity, and enhances blood circulation, boosting endurance and enabling gymnasts to maintain a high pace throughout the performance. Moreover, cardio training contributes to rapid recovery after intense workouts and competitions, which is important for optimal preparation for the next performance.

Thus, incorporating cardio training into gymnasts' training process is necessary for achieving outstanding results on the international stage of rhythmic gymnastics and provides them with a competitive advantage in the pursuit of medals and podium finishes.

Strength Training:

Strength training is important in preparing gymnasts for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. These workouts strengthen the muscle core, increase muscle strength and endurance, and enhance injury resilience. Successful execution of complex elements and compositions requires gymnasts to have high flexibility, grace, and strength, which provides stability and control during exercises.

Examples of Strength Training for Gymnasts	
Type of Exercise	Description
Bodyweight Exercises	Push-ups, pull-ups, crunches, lunges. These exercises develop strength and endurance of the entire body, improving movement control.
Dumbbell or Bodyweight Exercises	Squats, dumbbell presses, various pulling variations, etc. These exercises target the development of strength in specific muscle groups.
Utilization of Training Machines	Strength Working with machines for legs, arms, and core strengthens muscles and enhances overall strength endurance.

These strength training exercises help gymnasts develop the strength and endurance required for successful performances at international rhythmic gymnastics competitions.

Functional Training:

Functional training is essential in preparing gymnasts for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. It aims to develop the strength, flexibility, coordination, and stability needed for executing complex elements and compositions. Functional training is based on everyday movements and is characteristic of the sport, making it an effective tool for gymnasts' preparation.

These functional training exercises help gymnasts develop all aspects of physical preparation necessary for successful performances at international rhythmic gymnastics competitions.

Flexibility and Stretching:

Flexibility and stretching are crucial in preparing gymnasts for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. These aspects of physical preparation are integral to the training process and are key to successful competition performances.

- Improving Flexibility:

Flexibility is essential for executing complex acrobatic elements that require a wide range of motion. Flexibility allows gymnasts to perform elements quickly and gracefully, enhancing their performance's aesthetic appearance and impression.

Examples of Functional Training for Gymnasts	
№	Example
1	Jumps: forward, backward, sideways, rotational. Develop strength and endurance of the lower limbs, improve coordination, and stability during landing.
2	Rotations and turns: exercises involving torso rotations and turns in place or in motion. Help improve coordination and stability, as well as develop the ability to control one's body in space.
3	Balance exercises: performing on uneven surfaces or on balance platforms. Develop stability and steadiness in poses and movements, essential for executing elements on bars or balancing on balance apparatuses.
4	Lifts and carries: exercises involving lifting various objects or one's own body. Develop strength and endurance of muscles required for performing lifts and acrobatic elements.

- Injury Prevention:

Flexibility plays a vital role in injury prevention by improving joint mobility and reducing the risk of strains and muscle tears during the execution of tricks and elements.

- Development of Stretching:

Stretching helps increase flexibility and relax muscles after workouts, which promotes faster recovery and reduces muscle fatigue.

- Enhancing Expressiveness:

Flexibility and stretching enable gymnasts to perform more complex and beautiful movements, enhancing their aesthetics and expressiveness.

№	Examples of Flexibility and Stretching Exercises
1	Leg and Back Stretching: various split variations, forward and backward bends, side bends, leg presses to the body.
2	Arm and Shoulder Stretching: warm-up and stretching exercises for shoulder and elbow joints
3	Trunk Flexibility Exercises: back and side muscle stretching, torso rotation exercises.

Maintaining optimal flexibility and stretching is necessary for achieving success in rhythmic gymnastics and enables gymnasts to realize their full potential in competitions.

1. Progressive Training Load:

A progressive training load is crucial in preparing gymnasts for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. This training principle involves systematically increasing the intensity and volume of training throughout the training cycle to achieve optimal form by the time of competition.

- Gradual Increase in Intensity:

The training begins with relatively light and short workouts, allowing gymnasts to recover and adapt to new loads. Gradually, the intensity and duration of training increase, leading to improvements in physical fitness and adaptation to more complex training tasks.

2. Variety of Training Methods:

Progressive training load includes various training methods such as strength training, cardio workouts, functional exercises, flexibility, and stretching. This allows the development of different aspects of physical preparation and ensures a more comprehensive development of the gymnast.

3. Consideration of Individual Characteristics:

When planning the training process, it is important to consider each gymnast's individual characteristics. These include age, level of preparation, physical abilities, and health conditions to avoid overtraining and injuries.

4. Periodization of Training Cycle:

Training in rhythmic gymnastics is often based on periodization, where the training year is divided into phases of preparation, pre-competition training, competitions, and recovery. This allows gymnasts to peak at the right moment and ensures optimal use of training resources.

Progressive training load in rhythmic gymnastics is a key element of successful competition preparation. It allows gymnasts to develop all necessary physical qualities, achieve high results, and overcome challenges on the path to sporting success.

Progress in increasing training volume:

A week	Training volume (hours)
1	16
2	18
3	19
4	20
5	21
6	22
7	23
8	24

Analysis. This article provides a comprehensive overview of methods and strategies for developing endurance in gymnasts preparing for international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. By considering cardio workouts, strength training, functional exercises, flexibility work, and systematic training load, my article offers a comprehensive approach to athlete preparation that covers all aspects of physical conditioning.

One of the article's strengths is that it emphasizes the importance of integrating various types of training into the overall preparation program. For example, it highlights that strength training improves endurance, while functional exercises help develop strength, coordination, and stability. This comprehensive approach ensures a more complete and effective development of gymnasts.

It is also worth noting that the article considers the importance of each athlete's characteristics when planning the training process. This is important because the approach to training should be adapted to the athlete's level of preparation, physical capabilities, and goals.

Examples of exercises to develop endurance:

Type of workout	Examples of exercises
Cardio training	Running on a treadmill, exercise bike, jump rope
Power training	Pull-ups, push-ups, squats with dumbbells
Functional exercises	Deadlifts, burpees, jumping jacks
Flexibility and stretching	Splits, forward and side bends, floor stretches

Conclusion. Developing endurance is the cornerstone of successful gymnastic preparation in international rhythmic gymnastics competitions. Understanding and effectively utilizing various training methods to improve endurance are key to achieving outstanding competition results.

Cardiovascular training improves the cardiovascular system and increases endurance, enabling gymnasts to maintain a high pace and intensity throughout their performance. Strength training helps strengthen muscles and increase resistance to fatigue, which is particularly important when performing complex elements and acrobatic tricks.

Functional exercises develop strength, coordination, and stability, improving the technique of movement execution and allowing gymnasts to demonstrate more precise and efficient performances. Working on flexibility and stretching helps prevent injuries and enables gymnasts to perform elements with extraordinary grace and aesthetics.

Systematic training load plays an important role in gradually increasing gymnasts' physical preparedness and achieving optimal form by the time of competitions. This allows gymnasts to feel confident on the competitive stage and fully realize their potential.

Thus, combining these training methods provides gymnasts with the foundation for successful performances on the international stage of rhythmic gymnastics. Careful planning and systematic implementation of training programs enable gymnasts to achieve a high level of endurance, which is key to sporting success and achieving outstanding results on the world stage.

Sample plan for a training week:

Day of the week	Morning workout	Evening workout
Monday	Cardio training	Strength exercises
Tuesday	Functional exercises	Stretching and Flexibility
Wednesday	Cardio training	Strength exercises
Thursday	Functional exercises	Stretching and Flexibility
Friday	Cardio training	Strength exercises
Saturday	Stretching and Flexibility	Rest
Sunday	Rest	Rest

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